

اصطلاح "اهل السنة والجماعة" کی لغوی اور اصطلاحی شرح

THE LITERAL AND TERMINOLOGICAL EXPLANATION OF THE TERM "AHL-US-SUNNAH WA AL-JAMA'AH"

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ABSTRACT

The concept Ahl ul Sunnah wal Jama'ah, referring to a group of people, plays a pivotal role in the mainstream Islamic discourse. Any Islamic interpretation of a given matter will only be deemed authentic if it stems from the described source. This concept is a misconstrued one due to its many interpretations. A better understanding of this term reduces the perplexity regarding the objectively correct Islamic group. Increasing religious sects and task groups result in a common question about the certainty and authenticity of an Islamic group. This study is devoted to the appropriate explanation of the said terminology. Particular attention is paid to the lingual exploration of the components present in the term. A complete picture is presented through technical aspects explored on the topic.

This article begins with addressing each word of the phrase Ahl-us-Unnah Wa Al-Jama'ah separately, before beginning with a comparative study of its various Terminological meanings as mentioned by the subject experts, to arrive at a comprehensive definition. Various textual examples have been incorporated from the Qur'an and Sunnah for these literal and Terminological meanings. Furthermore, various applications of the term in the sacred text have been explored to grasp the meaning behind it as mentioned by the subject scholars. The article concludes with textual proofs from various renowned scholars and a summation of the entire discussion.

Keywords: Ahl-us-Unnah Wa Al-Jama'ah, Sunnah, Muslim, Jamat-ul-Muslimeen.

کلیدی الفاظ: اہل السنۃ والجماعۃ، مسلمان، جماعت المسلمین، فرقہ ناجیہ، الجماعۃ السواد الا عظیم۔

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